

Table S2: Mean grain size distribution (μm) in the bedload and floodplain sediments across the Yamuna mainstream. n/a: not available

Distance (km)	Bedload	Floodplain
	Mean grain size (μm)	Mean grain size (μm)
0	142	113
5	229	201
26	189	147
36	291	170
48	272	169
94	295	165
130	n/a	165
158	154	210
189	196	115
243	90.9	112
262	288	102
288	100	n/a
292	n/a	117
308	198	80
314	140	n/a
337	135	123
342	128	153
364	103	148
381	123	82.1
432	146	85.9
463	129	94.5
503	117	153
518	106	122
597	102	88
642	69	98
701	134	65
821	157	70
825	122	n/a
863	219	n/a
909	150	253
941	108	198
1000	396	167
1065	394	158
1069	158	102
1079	186	85
1101	473	145